

PREPSOIL WP5 - T.5.4. Capacity building for improved monitoring knowledge base

INTERNAL IDENTIFICATION OF POTENTIAL TRAINING TOPICS:

POTENTIAL TRAINING NEEDS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION AND TRANSPOSITION OF THE "SOIL MONITORING LAW"

Reference docs:

[Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience \(Soil Monitoring Law\)](#) (5 July 2023)

[General approach from the Council of the European Union](#) (17 June 2024)

1. LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

Proposed Content:

- **Details of the Directive and its relationship with other EU environmental regulations:** This includes understanding how the directive integrates with other environmental regulations and the broader EU regulatory framework.
- **Legal procedures for transposing the Directive into national legislation:** Guidance on how to adapt the provisions of the directive to national laws, including examples of best practices.
- **Rights and obligations of Member States:** Focus on the establishment of soil districts and the designation of competent authorities and "soil units."

Comments:

- **EC:** It is important to assess whether these topics are really necessary for Member States. A needs assessment can determine their relevance and adjust the content accordingly.

2. TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE OF SOIL AND ITS DESCRIPTORS

Proposed content:

- **Physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of soil:** Training in identifying and understanding key soil properties that affect its health and functionality.
- **Soil sampling and analysis methods:** Techniques for collecting representative samples and their laboratory analysis.
- **Interpretation of soil descriptors and soil health criteria:** Training in the use of indicators and thresholds to assess soil health.

Comments:

- **EC:** It is essential first to know how soil health indicators are estimated and then to be able to interpret these values with relevant reference data and thresholds.

- **PREPSOIL WP5:** Significant changes have occurred in biodiversity characterization in recent proposals. It is crucial to include harmonized sampling and analysis methods and consider the latest EU updates.

3. SOIL MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Proposed content:

- **Design and establishment of a soil monitoring framework:** Development of strategies for continuous and systematic soil monitoring.

This point is in line with point 1 of Article 23a of the Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law), which requires establishing a monitoring framework in accordance with Article 6 and determining sampling points as per Article 8(1) and (1a) and Part A.1 of Annex II.

- **Remote sensing techniques and use of spatial data:** Use of advanced technologies to collect data on soil status.
- **Soil health assessment and report preparation:** Methods to evaluate the collected information and present clear and accessible reports.

Comments:

- **EC:** Support in designing the sample survey and implementing quality management systems for laboratories is crucial.
- **PREPSOIL WP5:** Use examples of national monitoring systems in operation and consider PREPSOIL Deliverable T.4.2. The curriculum introduction should explain the concepts of soil health and quality.

4. SUSTAINABLE SOIL MANAGEMENT

Proposed content:

- **Principles and practices of sustainable soil management:** Focus on agricultural and forestry management techniques that preserve soil health.
- **Identification and mitigation of harmful management practices:** Training to identify and correct practices that harm the soil.
- **Implementation of soil regeneration practices:** Strategies for recovering degraded soils.

This point can benefit from the support indicated in Article 23a, points 2 and 6 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which establishes sustainable objective values and evaluates the critical loss of ecosystem services.

Comments:

- **PREPSOIL WP5:** It is vital to distinguish between agricultural fields and forest plots, and between types of soil degradation such as mineral and organic contamination.

5. MANAGEMENT OF CONTAMINATED SOILS

Proposed content:

- **Identification and assessment of potentially contaminated soils:** Methods to detect and assess soil contamination.

This point aligns with Article 23a, points 3 and 7 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which requires determining the list of organic pollutants and establishing a list of potentially contaminating activities.

- **Methodologies for investigating and managing soil contamination:** Procedures for treating and managing contaminated soils.
- **Development of action plans for the remediation of contaminated soils:** Creation of strategies for the recovery of soils affected by contaminants. This point also aligns with Article 23a, point 8.

Comments:

- **EC:** Consider integrating activities from existing projects like ARAGORN and ISLANDR.
- **PREPSOIL WP5:** A clear distinction must be made between types of soil contamination and degradation.

6. DIGITAL TOOLS AND DATA PORTAL

Proposed content:

- **Use of the digital data portal on soil health:** Training in accessing and using digital platforms for soil data management.
- **Integration of georeferenced data and its use in soil monitoring:** Use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for managing and analyzing spatial data.
- **Access and use of spatial databases:** Skills to access and use large spatial databases.

These points are supported by Article 23a, point 4 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which establishes the determination of values for soil sealing and soil destruction indicators.

Comments:

- **PREPSOIL WP5:** Clarify the differences between the subsections and ensure the protection of personal data in soil observations.

7. PUBLIC PARTICIPATION AND COMMUNICATION

Proposed content:

- **Effective communication strategies with the interested public:** Development of skills to communicate complex information in an accessible manner.
- **Transparency and access to environmental information:** Ensuring that information on soil health is transparent and accessible.
- **Procedures for public participation in decision-making:** Engaging the community and stakeholders in the decision-making process on soil management.

This point can be strengthened by Article 23a, point 5 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which establishes the determination or estimation of soil descriptors' values.

Comments:

- **EC:** Guidelines for training soil managers, landowners, and relevant authorities are essential.
- **PREPSOIL WP5:** Public participation is crucial for accessing information and contributing to data acquisition.

8. EVALUATION AND MONITORING OF IMPLEMENTATION

Proposed content:

- **Monitoring and evaluation techniques for the implementation of the Directive:** Methods to evaluate compliance and effectiveness of the directive.

This point aligns with Article 23a, point 1 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which requires establishing a monitoring framework.

- **Performance indicators and trend evaluation:** Use of indicators to measure progress and long-term trends.
- **Reporting and documenting progress:** Training in writing reports and documenting advances in implementation.

Annex 3.2. Report on training needs for pilot courses on soil health indicators and the existing policy framework

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DRAFT PROGRAMME FOR PILOT TRAININGS ON SOIL HEALTH INDICATORS AND THE CURRENT REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

GENERAL OBJECTIVE OF THE PROGRAM

The main objective of the program is to train public officials who manage or will manage soil health data under a unified reporting system, policymakers who make decisions based on these indicators, and members of Living Labs who drive innovation and co-creation of solutions, by providing a comprehensive understanding of soil health indicators and their application within a continuously evolving regulatory and technical framework.

Participants will aim to:

- Develop an in-depth knowledge of soil functions and their role in environmental, food, and climate sustainability.
- Understand the complexity and challenges associated with defining, measuring, and applying indicators, particularly in diverse contexts such as geographic regions and specific land uses.
- Critically analyze the advances and limitations of the **Soil Monitoring Law (SML)** and the **Mission Soil initiatives**, promoting flexible and adaptive approaches that address local needs while maintaining harmonized European-level objectives.
- Acquire practical tools to implement monitoring strategies and formulate public policies based on scientific evidence and robust data.

This program combines theoretical and practical training to empower policymakers to make informed decisions, considering both the opportunities and challenges faced by soil management in Europe and globally.

DETAILED PROGRAMME

MODULE 1: FOUNDATIONS AND GLOBAL CONTEXT

[Presentation 1: Soil Health in the 21st Century](#)

Objective: Establish a conceptual framework on the importance of soil and the global challenges associated with its management.

Contents:

- **Functions and ecosystem services of soil:** Ecosystem services according to FAO: supply of food, fibers, and fuels. Habitat for organisms. Flood regulation. Source of pharmaceuticals and genetic resources. Basis for human infrastructure. Supply of construction materials. Cultural heritage. Carbon retention. Water purification and reduction of soil contaminants. Climate regulation. Nutrient cycling.
- **Main global threats:** Erosion, compaction, acidification, contamination, sealing, salinization, waterlogging, nutrient imbalance (deficiency or excess), and loss of organic carbon and biodiversity.
- **Emerging challenges:** climate change, emerging pollutants (e.g., PFAS, microplastics).
- **Global perspective:** United Nations initiatives: Sustainable Development Goals, FAO, and IPCC.
- **European perspective:** EU initiatives, including the Soil Monitoring Law (SML), Mission Soil. "Farm to Fork" Strategy, EU Soil Strategy for 2030, Biodiversity Strategy, Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture, and Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation.
 - **SML:**
 - Main objectives, structure, and proposal of key indicators.
 - Concerns raised by Member States: Harmonization vs. local flexibility. Integration of the directive with existing national initiatives. Sampling strategies. The use of a single threshold to define healthy/unhealthy soils. Definition of different health levels.
 - **Mission Soil:**
 - Living Labs and Lighthouses as experimental and demonstrative environments.
 - Applied technological tools: Remote sensing, GIS, digital platforms.
 - Normative and technical impact: Connection between SML, Mission Soil, and local needs.

Group Debate: What local challenges do soils face in your regions? Example: Soil artificialization.

MODULE 2: KEY INDICATORS AND THEIR COMPLEXITY

[Presentation 2: Key Indicators and Their Complexity](#)

Objective: Understand the scientific and technical basis behind soil health indicators and the challenges in their application.

Contents:

- **Physical indicators:** Bulk density, structural stability, water retention capacity, erosion rate, porosity, depth of topsoil horizon, infiltration and runoff, penetration resistance, among others.
- **Chemical indicators:** Soil Organic Carbon (SOC), salinity, pH, contamination, nutrients, cation exchange capacity, exchangeable cations, and others.

- **Biological indicators:** Microbial biodiversity, basal respiration, enzymatic activity.
- **Detailed study of the indicators proposed in the SML:**
 - SOC, biodiversity, bulk density, sealing, erosion, salinity and contamination, nutrient excess, subsoil compaction, reduction of soil water retention capacity, acidification, arable layer compaction, soil biodiversity loss, land occupation, and sealing.
 - Analysis of their relevance and applicability in different contexts and types of land use. Uncertainty/precision of the indicators.
 - Evaluation of how harmonized thresholds may influence national and regional policies.
- **The need for flexible approaches that consider regional particularities and land uses.** Emphasizing a holistic vision to address problems (avoiding the unintended exacerbation of other issues while trying to control a specific one). For example, carbon content can be increased by adding more nitrogen, but this may lead to eutrophication or GHG emissions.
- **Directed questions:** Which indicators are most relevant in specific contexts?

MODULE 3: MONITORING METHODS AND ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES

Presentation 3: Monitoring Methods

Objective: Explain how to conduct soil health indicator monitoring, from planning to implementation, ensuring representativeness and accuracy.

Contents:

- **Basic principles for indicator monitoring:**
 - Clear objective definition according to local and regional contexts.
 - Identification of key indicators to monitor (SOC, biodiversity, salinity, among others). **It may be necessary to distinguish between indicators that are relevant to measure in all soils (e.g., SOC, structural stability, biodiversity, etc.) and indicators that are only relevant to measure in certain contexts (salinity, certain types of contamination, etc.).**
- **Designing representative monitoring plans:**
 - Selection of sampling points based on degradation risks and spatial representativeness.
 - Monitoring frequency to ensure updated data.
- **Practical methods for data collection:**
 - Manual and traditional procedures adapted to different contexts.
 - Integration of adaptive approaches based on soil type (agricultural, forest, urban, mixed).
- **Preparation of a basic monitoring plan adapted to a case study.**

Presentation 4: Digital Technologies for Monitoring and Data Analysis

Objective: Provide participants with information on digital and technological tools needed to monitor and analyze soil health indicators accurately and efficiently.

Contents:

- **Using the digital soil health data portal:**
 - Training on access and use of digital platforms for soil data management.
- **Integration of georeferenced data and its use in indicator monitoring:**
 - Use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to manage and analyze spatial data.
- **Advanced technologies as support:**
 - Remote sensing for capturing high-resolution data and integrating it into digital platforms.
 - In-situ sensors connected to digital systems for continuous monitoring of chemical and biological indicators.
- **Accessing and using large spatial databases:**
 - Developing skills to access, analyze, and utilize spatial databases in the context of soil monitoring.
- **Relation to Article 23a, Point 4 of the SML:** Determination of values for indicators such as sealing and soil destruction through digital integration.

MODULE 4: INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS AND DECISION-MAKING

Presentation 5: Indicator Evaluation and Report Preparation

Objective: Train participants in the critical interpretation of data and effective communication of results. Explore how to integrate results into the formulation of effective public policies.

Contents:

- **Evaluation of scenarios and analysis of the impact of different land management strategies** (agricultural practices, forestry, etc.), with application of models for evidence-based decision-making.
- **Comparative interpretation:** Normative thresholds and local adaptations.
- **Success examples in the implementation of soil policies based on data.**